

A User's Study on Quality in Library Services in Engineering Colleges at Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu

R. Suganthi

Research Scholar, Tamil University, Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu, India

Dr. T. Sivakumar

Research Guide and Assistant Librarian, Tamil University, Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract

In this paper details regarding user research in Library services of engineering colleges at Thanjavur district, Tamil Nadu are given. The survey has been taken in 12 Engineering Library College. The method used to collect the data is in the form of questionnaire. The questions are based on the access to full text database in the library, access to digital repository, provision of books to the users, facilities and services offered by the library, and library staff supporting in the discovery of information. All the users wished to receive the basic services, honesty, reliability, responsiveness, conversation with them, timeliness and a caring approach. They need help to be able to access information as well as print and online versions of the materials.

Keywords: *Full Text Data Base, Users Study, Institutional Repository, Facilities & Services*

Introduction

Library Services are evolving to meet the changing needs of society, transforming from traditional information stores to Learning Resource Centres. Libraries are adapting to ICT applications and clientele's information seeking behavior, focusing on providing the right information at the right time to improve society. The efficiency of libraries depends on their librarians, who implement and support modern technology, ensuring the right information is provided to the right people at the right time. As society changes, libraries must adapt to meet the evolving needs of their users and staff.

The researcher, the scientist, the teacher, the students, the industrial and business personalities, the Politicians, the farmer and common people of all the corner of the society. Libraries are in a state of transition, and all needs rely upon information for the formatting of this revolution. Practitioners are confronted with so many challenges which could be attributed to the advent of information communication technologies as well as its development.

Objectives

- It is for the purpose of determining the extent of users satisfaction level on the full text databases available in the library.
- In order to know the degree of support by the library staff in discovering the information.
- It is undertaken to find the satisfaction level of the users concerning the facilities and services

provided by Library.

Methodology

The researcher adopted the questionnaire method and compiled a questionnaire that was administered to students and faculties of engineering college libraries. They are satisfied or not as their questions based on their opinion about the library facilities. The number of population under study was very large and only 2100 users (students and faculties) were contacted who were given the questionnaires. Quantitative data analysis with regards to the collected data through the questionnaires was properly made and interpreted.

Data Analysis

Table 1 User Category

User Category	No of respondents	Percentage of respondents
UG students	920	43.81
PG students	638	30.38
Assistant Professor	210	10.00
Associate Professor	160	7.62
Professor	172	8.19
Total	2100	100.00

Table I indicates the Uses Category wise distribution of respondents. It could be noted that out of the total 2100 respondents, UG students 43.81% and PG students 30.38%, 8.19% are Professors, 7.62% are Associate Professors and the remaining 10% respondents are Assistant Professors.

Table 2 Access to Full Text Database in Library

Subject gateways/portals	No of respondents	Percentage of respondents
ABI / INFORM	120	5.71
ACM Digital Library	38	1.81
AICTE Indest	16	0.76
Applied Science & Tech Plus	80	3.80
ASCE On-line Journals	72	3.42
ASME On-line Journals	58	2.76
ASTM Standards	44	2.09
Capitaline	68	3.23
EBSCO Business Source premier	18	0.85
Emerald Full Text	68	3.23
Engineering Village 2	48	2.28
Euro Monitor (GMD)	42	2.00
IEEE	72	3.42
INSPEC	330	15.71
JCCC	111	5.28

J-GATE	79	3.76
Nature	50	2.38
Science Direct	130	6.19
SciFinder scholar Mathscinet	212	10.09
UGC Infonet	166	7.90
Web of knowledge	260	12.38
Other specify	18	0.85
Total	2100	100.00

Table 2 shows that out of 2100 respondents 260 (12.38%) respondents accessed Web of knowledge database, 330 (15.71%) respondents used INSPEC, SciFinder scholar Mathscinet database was used by 212 (10.09%) respondents.

Table 3 Access to e - Resources

Place of Accessing e - Resources	No of respondents	% of respondents
CD / DVD Database	185	8.81
e-resources	560	26.67
Networks Based Services	470	22.38
Internet Services	885	42.14
Total	2100	100.00

Table 3 describes about the access to digital repository. Majority of the respondents (42.14%) accessed internet, 560 respondents utilized e - resources, 470 respondents accessed Networks Based Services repository, 185 respondents accessed CD / DVD Database.

Table 4 Books Issued to the Users

User Opinion	No of respondents	% of respondents
Sufficient	1285	61.19
Very sufficient	752	35.81
Insufficient	63	3.00
Total	2100	100.00

From the above table 4, we describe about the user’s opinion on books issued for home reading. It was found that 1285 (61.19) respondents had their views that the number of books and loan period are sufficient for their study and 752 (35.81) respondents have given their view that the number of books and loan period are very sufficient and 63 (3%) respondents have an opinion that the number of books issued by the library is insufficient.

Table 5 Users Satisfaction on Overdue Charges

User Satisfaction	No of respondents	% of respondents
Moderate	1005	47.86
High	442	21.05
Very high	653	31.09
Total	2100	100.00

Above table 5 provides details related to the users’ satisfaction on overdue charges. Among the 2100 respondents, out of which 1005 (47.86) respondents had their satisfaction with the overdue charges collected by Library if the books were not returned on time with the level of Moderate, 442 (21.05) had a good satisfaction level and 653 (31.09) had very high satisfaction level towards overdue charges.

Table 6 User’s Opinions on Library Staff for Discovering the Information

User Opinion	No of respondents	% of respondents
Always	1085	51.67
Often	752	35.81
Rarely	203	9.67
Never	60	2.85
Total	2100	100.00

Table 6 about the user’s opinion about library staff in supporting and discovering information is given. A majority of the respondents (51.67%) has given an opinion that the library staff always support in discovering the information but 752 (35.81%), 203 (9.67%) provided their opinion as Often and Rarely respectively in supporting them to discover the information. Out of all respondents, only 2.85% of opinion that the library staff do not support in the finding of the resources.

Table 7 Users’ Satisfactory on Facilities and Services Offered by the Library

User Satisfaction	No of respondents	% of respondents
Good	1209	57.57
Satisfactory	738	35.14
Not Satisfactory	153	7.29
Total	2100	100.00

The above table 7 explains services and facilities offered by the library of which the users are satisfied. A majority of 57.57 % of the respondents give an opinion of good as far as facilities and services rendered by the library is concerned, while 735 (35.14%) and 153 (7.29%) give the opinion as Satisfactory and not satisfactory respectively.

Conclusion

But libraries have new challenges to face, namely changing client bases, different formats for information and changing teaching methods. Lack of survey of existing services shows these users are relatively unaware of what exists already, and relatively little is done to understand the needs of users, through services. Users want basic services, credibility, responsiveness, timeliness, honesty, and care. Information access is what they need, in print and online formats as well.

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